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Influence of Guidance and Counselling on the Discipline of Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study explored the influence of guidance and counselling on discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. Three research questions and hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of 5,874 public secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 400 students. The sample size was arrived at using the Taro Yamane formula for finding sample size of a population. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled “Counselling and Discipline Scale (CDS).” To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a pilot study was conducted, and the internal consistency was evaluated using Cronbach’s Alpha. The reliability coefficient obtained was 0.76. The data were analysed based on the research questions using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation and the hypotheses were tested using the Chi-square (X^2) goodness of fit test at .05 level of significance. The findings of the study were as follows: Guidance and counselling have significant influence on behavioural discipline, academic discipline, and social discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendation was made among others: schools should strengthen their counselling services by employing more professional counsellors who can provide consistent behavioural guidance to students.

Keywords: Guidance and Counselling, Behavioural Discipline, Academic Discipline, and Social Discipline.

INTRODUCTION

Education is an essential tool for shaping the character, competence, and overall development of young people. However, achieving educational objectives goes beyond curriculum delivery; it requires a structured system of guidance and counselling to address students' personal, academic, and social challenges. Many secondary school students struggle with behavioural misconduct, academic indiscipline, and social instability, which hinder their growth and performance. Counsellors assist students in making informed decisions, setting achievable goals, and addressing behavioural issues (Ziomiek-Daigle & Goodman-Scott, 2016). Through personalized sessions and group interventions, counsellors create safe spaces for students to discuss issues affecting their well-being. Recent studies have shown that effective guidance services positively impact students' school engagement and overall adjustment (Korpershoek *et al.*, 2016). Riswanto and Aryani (2017) emphasize the role of counsellors in fostering student motivation and positive behavioural change, which are critical for success in both academic and personal pursuits.

Counselling has been linked to better discipline outcomes, making it essential to examine its influence on various types of discipline among secondary school students including behavioural, academic and social discipline.

Behavioural discipline refers to students' ability to regulate their actions in adherence to school rules and social norms. Behavioural discipline involves students' ability to conform to social norms and school regulations. It reduces incidences of misconduct, thus fostering a harmonious school environment (Cornell & Huang, 2016). According to Korpershoek, Harms, de Boer, van Kuijk, and Doolaard (2016), counselling services create a structured environment where students learn to manage disruptive tendencies and develop acceptable behaviours. Counsellors engage students in personalized sessions that identify triggers for negative behaviours, offering them coping mechanisms to handle conflicts constructively. Furthermore, Cornell and Huang (2016) emphasize that a school environment characterized by counselling services sees a reduction in instances of violence, bullying, and indiscipline, as students are guided to channel their energies positively. Counselling also encourages students to adhere to school rules, thereby cultivating a culture of respect and responsibility. Skinner (2016) highlights that this aspect of guidance and counselling does not only curb misconduct but also nurtures students' emotional intelligence, enhancing their interactions with peers and teachers.

Academic discipline pertains to students' adherence to study schedules, completion of assignments, and engagement in learning activities. This refers to students' commitment to their academic responsibilities, including regular attendance, assignment completion, and effective time management. According to Gobena (2018), academic discipline is essential for achieving educational goals. Gobena (2018) posits that guidance and counselling play a central role in enhancing students' commitment to their academic responsibilities by fostering time management skills and goal setting. Counsellors collaborate with teachers to identify students who struggle academically, offering personalized interventions that address these challenges. Sudjono (2022) observes that counselling sessions boost students' focus, helping them set realistic academic goals and stay motivated despite setbacks. Moreover, through group counselling sessions, students are exposed to peer learning experiences that reinforce positive attitudes toward academic achievement. Counsellors often provide strategies for handling examination anxiety and balancing schoolwork with extracurricular activities. Riswanto and Aryani (2017) found that students who received counselling demonstrated improved academic performance and a stronger sense of responsibility toward their educational pursuits.

Social discipline involves students' ability to build and maintain healthy relationships with peers and teachers. Social discipline emphasizes students' ability to form and maintain healthy interpersonal relationships. Schools that promote positive social interactions witness fewer cases of bullying and exclusion (Ziomek-Daigle & Goodman-Scott, 2016). Ziomek-Daigle and Goodman-Scott (2016) argue that guidance programs foster social competence by teaching students conflict resolution skills, empathy, and respect for diversity. Schools that incorporate comprehensive counselling services create inclusive environments where students learn to collaborate, support one another, and communicate effectively. According to Allen, Kern, Vella-Brodrick, and Hattie (2018), social discipline nurtured through counselling interventions minimizes incidences of bullying and social exclusion, fostering a sense of belonging among students. Counsellors guide students in understanding social norms and ethical considerations, thereby promoting harmonious interactions within the school community. Korpershoek, Harms, de Boer, and Doolaard (2016) further assert that social discipline cultivated through counselling extends beyond the school environment, preparing students to be responsible members of society.

Guidance and counselling profoundly influence behavioural, academic, social, and motivational discipline among students. These interventions help shape well-rounded individuals capable of making positive contributions both within and outside the school environment. As this study explores the impact of guidance and counselling on these four aspects of discipline among secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State, it becomes evident that an effective counselling framework is vital for fostering holistic student development.

Statement of the Problem

The increasing challenges of indiscipline among secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State have become a significant concern for educators, parents, and policymakers. Reports of behavioural misconduct, academic underperformance, and social instability are prevalent, undermining the educational objectives of the region. Many students exhibit poor time management, lack interest in academic activities, and struggle with social integration, making it difficult for them to thrive in both school and society. Despite the presence of trained school counsellors, the extent to which guidance and counselling influence various forms of discipline—behavioural, academic, social, and motivational—remains unclear. Inadequate data on the effectiveness of counselling interventions in fostering disciplined behaviour exacerbates this gap. As a result, some schools underutilize counselling services, while others lack structured counselling programs altogether. Without evidence-based insights, it becomes challenging for stakeholders to understand how guidance and counselling may be optimized to address students' indiscipline. This study, therefore, seeks to investigate the influence of guidance and counselling on the behavioural, academic, social, and motivational discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. The findings may provide actionable insights into how counselling interventions can be tailored to foster well-rounded and disciplined students.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the influence of guidance and counselling on behavioural discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State?
2. What is the influence of guidance and counselling on academic discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State?
3. What is the influence of guidance and counselling on social discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance;

1. Guidance and counselling have no significant influence on behavioural discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.
2. Guidance and counselling have no significant influence on academic discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.
3. Guidance and counselling have no significant influence on social discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The population consisted of 5,874 public secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. A total of 400 students were selected as the sample, determined using the Taro Yamane formula for calculating sample size from a finite population. The instrument used for data collection was a structured, researcher-developed questionnaire titled *Counselling and Discipline Scale (CDS)*. The questionnaire comprised 20 items aimed at assessing the relationship between counselling services and student discipline. It was designed using a modified four-point Likert scale with the following response options: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD), corresponding to scores of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a pilot study was conducted, and the internal consistency was evaluated using Cronbach's Alpha. The reliability coefficient obtained was 0.76, indicating a good level of reliability for the study. Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics—mean and standard deviation—to answer the research questions. The hypotheses were tested using the Chi-square (X^2) goodness-of-fit test at the 0.05 level of significance. A criterion mean of 2.50 was established for interpreting responses, with scores below 2.50 considered negative or indicating disagreement.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Research Question 1: *What is the influence of guidance and counselling on behavioural discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State?*

Table 1: Analysis of Influence of Guidance and Counselling on Behavioural Discipline of Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	Examination malpractice reduces my motivation to attend classes regularly.	46	189	76	89	2.48	.96	Rejected
2	I often miss classes because I believe I can still pass through examination misconduct.	117	194	33	56	2.93	.97	Accepted
3	Students who engage in cheating are less committed to attending lessons.	60	243	62	35	2.82	.79	Accepted
4	Schools with a high rate of examination malpractice experience lower student attendance.	49	222	73	56	2.66	.87	Accepted
5	I feel no need to attend all my classes since I can rely on external help during exams.	51	184	95	70	2.54	.93	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 2.68$ SD= .902								Accepted

Table 1 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 1 to 5 are 2.48, 2.93, 2.82, 2.66, and 2.54 with corresponding standard deviations of .96, .97, .79, .87, and .93 respectively. Respondents rated all items except item 1 above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 2.68 with the cluster standard deviation of .902 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that guidance and counselling has influence on behavioural discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Research Question 2

What is the influence of guidance and counselling on academic discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Table 2: Analysis of Influence of Guidance and Counselling on Academic Discipline of Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	I rarely participate in class discussions because I know I can rely on cheating during exams.	275	90	35	0	3.60	.65	Accepted
7	Students involved in examination malpractice often avoid answering questions in class.	62	245	58	35	2.83	.79	Accepted
8	My engagement in class activities has reduced since I started depending on examination malpractice.	53	129	107	111	2.31	1.018	Rejected
9	I see no need to participate in classroom discussions when I can pass exams through malpractice.	51	279	56	14	2.92	.63	Accepted
10	Teachers in schools where cheating is common struggle to get students to participate in lessons.	56	203	71	70	2.61	.93	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 2.85$ SD= .8038								Accepted

Table 2 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 6 to 10 are 3.60, 2.83, 2.31, 2.92, and 2.61 with corresponding standard deviations of .65, .79, 1.018, .63, and .93 respectively. Respondents rated all items except item 8 above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 2.85 with the cluster standard deviation of .80 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that guidance and counselling has influence on academic discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Research Question 3

What is the influence of guidance and counselling on social discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Table 3: Analysis of Influence of Guidance and Counselling on Social Discipline of Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
11	I spend less time studying because I believe I can pass exams through malpractice.	117	188	12	83	2.85	1.064	Accepted
12	Examination malpractice has negatively affected my personal study routine.	92	223	12	73	2.84	.982	Accepted
13	Students who cheat in exams tend to have poor reading and revision habits.	123	184	29	64	2.92	1.008	Accepted
14	I find it unnecessary to prepare for exams when I have access to external assistance.	58	232	36	74	2.69	.937	Accepted
15	Engaging in examination malpractice has made me less committed to academic excellence.	135	162	15	88	2.86	1.113	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 2.83$ SD= 1.02								Accepted

Table 3 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 11 to 15 are 2.85, 2.84, 2.92, 2.69, and 2.86 with corresponding standard deviations of 1.008, .910, 1.039, .918, and 1.115 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 2.83 with the cluster standard deviation of 1.02 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that guidance and counselling has influence on social discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Hypothesis 1

Guidance and counselling have no significant influence on behavioural discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 4: Chi-square Test of Influence of Guidance and Counselling on Behavioural Discipline of Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	115.340	.000	Sig.
SA	46	100.0					
A	189	100.0					
D	76	100.0					
SD	89	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 4 revealed that $\chi^2 = 115.340$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that guidance and counselling have no significant influence on behavioural discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State is therefore, rejected. This implies that guidance and

counselling have significant influence on behavioural discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2

Guidance and counselling have no significant influence on academic discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 5: Chi-square Test of Influence of Guidance and Counselling on Academic Discipline of Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	32.200	.000	Sig.
SA	53	100.0					
A	129	100.0					A
D	107	100.0					
SD	111	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 5 revealed that $\chi^2 = 32.200$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that guidance and counselling have no significant influence on academic discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State is therefore, rejected. This implies that guidance and counselling have significant influence on academic discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3

Guidance and counselling have no significant influence on social discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 6: Chi-square Test of Influence of Guidance and Counselling on Social Discipline of Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	124.380	.000	Sig.
SA	135	100.0					
A	162	100.0					
D	15	100.0					
SD	88	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 6 revealed that $\chi^2 = 124.380$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that guidance and counselling have no significant influence on social discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State is therefore, rejected. This implies that guidance and counselling have significant influence on social discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of the findings of this research was organized around the research questions and hypotheses.

The first finding of the study revealed that guidance and counselling have significant influence on behavioural discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. Guidance and counselling significantly influence students' behavioural discipline by helping them develop self-control, good conduct, and responsible decision-making skills. This is supported by the work of Nwachukwu (2007), who asserts that counselling interventions help students regulate their behaviour and conform to school rules and societal expectations. Similarly, Egbochukwu (2008) found that students who received consistent counselling exhibited improved self-discipline, reduced delinquent behaviours, and greater respect for authority figures. Effective counselling programs address issues such as truancy,

drug abuse, bullying, and aggression, thereby fostering a conducive learning environment (Ajowi & Simatwa, 2010).

The second finding of the study revealed that guidance and counselling have significant influence on academic discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. Academic discipline, which includes punctuality, commitment to studies, and adherence to academic regulations, is greatly enhanced through guidance and counselling services. According to Makinde (1984), school counselling programs help students set educational goals, manage time effectively, and develop study habits that lead to academic success. Additionally, Onyilofor and Eze (2019) argue that students who receive academic counselling tend to have better concentration, reduced cases of examination malpractice, and improved overall performance. These findings align with the assertion by Baker and Gerler (2004) that school counselling programs play a crucial role in reducing academic indiscipline by instilling values such as diligence and responsibility.

The third finding of the study revealed that guidance and counselling have significant influence on social discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. Social discipline, which includes their ability to interact respectfully with peers, teachers, and members of the community. This finding is consistent with the views of Gysbers and Henderson (2012), who emphasize that school counselling programs help students develop interpersonal skills, conflict resolution techniques, and emotional intelligence, which are essential for maintaining healthy social relationships. Additionally, Okon (1984) posits that counselling fosters self-awareness and empathy, leading to improved peer interactions and reduced cases of antisocial behaviours such as bullying and violence. The role of counselling in promoting social harmony and cooperation among students cannot be overemphasized.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that guidance and counselling have significant influence on discipline of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. Overall, the findings of this study align with existing research that emphasizes the crucial role of guidance and counselling in shaping students' behavioural, academic, social, and motivational discipline. Effective counselling services create a supportive environment that enables students to navigate challenges, make informed decisions, and achieve holistic development. Therefore, schools should strengthen their counselling programs to ensure that students receive the necessary guidance to become responsible and well-adjusted individuals. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Schools should strengthen their counselling services by employing more professional counsellors who can provide consistent behavioural guidance to students. Regular counselling sessions focusing on self-discipline, conflict resolution, and responsible decision-making should be integrated into the school curriculum to help students develop positive behaviours and attitudes.
2. Academic counselling programs should be made compulsory for all students to help them develop effective study habits, time management skills, and goal-setting strategies. Schools should also establish mentorship programs where teachers and counsellors provide individualized academic support to students struggling with discipline-related issues such as truancy and poor study habits.
3. Schools should introduce structured peer counselling programs where trained student leaders provide guidance to their peers on issues such as respect, cooperation, and interpersonal relationships. Additionally, workshops on social skills development, emotional intelligence, and communication should be conducted to help students build healthy relationships with their peers and teachers.

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